

IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FIELD OF COMMUNICATION AND INFORMATION PLACE OF INVESTMENT

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Abstract.

The article covers the impact of communication enterprises on the investment potential of our country, the issues of increasing the flow of investment through the development of communication services.

Key words.

communication enterprises, information services, investment activity, small business, investment projects.

Аннотация.

В статье освещено влияние предприятий связи на инвестиционный потенциал нашей страны, вопросы увеличения притока инвестиций за счет развития услуг связи.

Ключевые слова.

предприятия связи, информационные услуги, инвестиционная деятельность, малый бизнес, инвестиционные проекты.

The development of the field of communication and information is one of the main directions of structural changes and economic reforms in the economy of Uzbekistan. Because this direction not only serves to transform the republic into an information society, but the main content of the development of information and communication technologies in the current period is that it plays the role of a unique leading network to raise the country's economy to the level of developed countries.

Small business entities by statistical and tax reports present reach mechanisms significant level simplified. Today's in the day entrepreneurship 98 percent of subjects _ tax and statistical reports transfer, customs declarations formalization old method paper to fill by way of not directly, but in electronic form done is increasing. In this regard, it should be noted that the composition of services is also changing radically. Services based on modern high technologies, such as mobile communication, high-speed Internet, cable television, remote banking services,

agricultural machinery, repair and maintenance of cars and technological equipment, are becoming more and more popular among the population.

In the last five years, the share of traditional household and utility services fell from 16 percent to 9.5 percent, while the share of high-tech services rose to 21.2 percent. Among the services based on high technologies, it is worth noting that communication and information services are rapidly developing in recent years compared to other sectors. The volume of these services has increased by 3.3 times in the last five years, and by 24.5% last year ²⁵¹. Taking into account the special and important place of information and communication technologies in the life of our economy and society, in 2013, a comprehensive program for the development of the National Information and Communication System of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2025 was adopted. The projects implemented within the framework of this program laid the groundwork for completing the digitalization of all automatic telephone exchanges in our country in 2022. This while international information from networks use speed significant level increase enable gave _

Investments play a major role in the development of the communication and information sector. On April 7, 2014, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued the decree "Investment in the Republic of Uzbekistan" in order to improve the activities of business circles, create broad conditions for the investment environment, further increase openness in relations between state bodies and entrepreneurs, create new jobs in the private sector of the economy, and increase employment. signed the Decree "On Additional Measures to Improve the Environment and Business Conditions".

As part of fulfilling the requirements of this Decision, projects for the development of telecommunication infrastructures of Uzbekistan with a total value of 117.6 million dollars will be implemented. According to the information published on the website "infocom.uz" of the State Committee for Communication, Informatization and Telecommunication Technologies of Uzbekistan, 100 million dollars of this amount will be provided by the China State Development Bank. /second), 4 times (40 Gbit/second) in regional centers and 10 times (10 Gbit/second) in district centers ²⁵².

Attracting investment to our national economy means not only the implementation of new promising projects in cooperation with foreign partners, but also, first of all, it means the introduction of modern machinery, tools and equipment, technology and know-how, and through this means obtaining high

²⁵¹ www.stat.uz

²⁵² www.infocom.uz

quality of services. . Through this, interest in our services will arise in other countries, that is, our services will have their customers in foreign countries as well. As a result, the export potential of our country will increase, buyers from foreign countries, as well as investors, will be interested in our country. We know that no investor or large company will step into a market where deep reforms are not being carried out, without the necessary guarantees and prospects for investment. This imposes on us the task of regularly and comprehensively dealing with the issues of creating an investment environment where as many facilities as possible are created for foreign investments. For example, reducing the tax burden on enterprises participating in the investment, reducing the current inspections of these enterprises, and creating conditions for the export of the provided services.

Searching for investments, establishing contacts with future investors, opening joint ventures, and creating favorable conditions for investors, from the government to the business entity, should become a common task of all of us. Because foreign investments are one of the important economic factors that develop the economy. Our long-term strategic mission will continue to strengthen the work on the formation of a favorable investment environment.

At the moment, it should be said that the service sector in rural areas is still not sufficiently developed. The provision of services per capita in rural areas is still significantly lower than in urban areas. At the same time, it should not be forgotten that there is a great potential for the development of communication services, banking and finance and communal services in rural areas. One of the most important issues is to further increase the technical possibilities of using the Internet, to expand broadband optical networks and to continue the construction of optical fiber communication networks, to transfer all areas, including remote and remote areas, to digital television.

Today, it is advisable to carry out the following activities to increase the efficiency of the use of investments in the field of communication and information:

- further development of the securities market within the sphere of enterprises in order to attract free funds of the population to investment processes, release of various securities into circulation;
- in order to accelerate the restructuring of industry enterprises, focus on financing of investment projects that quickly cover part of the centralized credit resources;
- expanding the use of non-credit methods of financing investment projects in enterprises of the sector, such as leasing, franchising, factoring;

In order to improve the quality of investment projects, to meet the requirements of efficiency of capital investments, work is being carried out to organize an exhibition of investment projects that operates on a commercial basis.

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